

The Effect of Financial Innovations on Financial Performance of Banks: The Case of Commercial Banks in Ethiopia

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of financial innovations on the financial performance of commercial banks in Ethiopia. The researcher used an explanatory study to assess the impact of financial innovation on profitability. The study observes the effect of financial innovations on the net interest margin as the fundamental index of profitability. The study uses annual reports or financial statements of all Ethiopian commercial banks covering the period from 2016 to 2020. The explanatory variables are identified to reveal their relationship and influence on the financial performance of banks. These independent variables are the number of ATM Machines, the number of POS Terminals, and the number of international cardholders. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The researcher used linear regression model with the aid of SPSS version 21. Three explanatory variables were included in this study, and out of these, two variables are found to have a statistically significant impact on the financial performance of banks. These variables are a number of ATM Machines and the number of POS Terminals. Considering these findings, the researcher recommends those commercial banks exert more efforts on the establishment of ATM across the country, to expand POS terminals, create awareness about financial innovation services, and keep up on introducing and implementing financial innovations across the country.

Key Words: Financial innovation, financial performance, ATM, POS, NIM

1. Introduction

The financial system in all economies is composed of the bank-based system where provision and monitoring of investments funds are made through the banks on the one hand and the stock market where investors (surplus units) enter directly through ownership of securities. Banks play an intermediary role in mobilizing funds from savers and subsequently lend them to investors-individual/corporations. Banks play a crucial role in improving economic efficiency by channeling funds from resource surplus units to better productive investment opportunities. Banks also play an important role in the trade and payment systems by significantly reducing transaction costs and increasing convenience [37].

In less monetized countries, the financial sector is dominated by banking industry; effective and efficient functioning of the latter has a significant role in accelerating economic growth. The sector that has been most radically affected by the information technology developments is the banking system. Information technology has become a critical business resource because of its absence could result in poor decisions and, ultimately, business failure. Technology has opened up new markets, new products, new services, and efficient delivery channels for the banking industry [13].

As per [19], the Ethiopian banking system is very much behind in the adoption of financial innovations compared to the rest world. But, the Ethiopian financial sector cannot remain an exception in expanding the use of the system. In her study, Rahel [42] had stated the benefits of technological innovations like E-banking are well known by the banks and represent a formidable force to driven implementation of the E-banking systems. To this end, the current study has tried to show the effects of financial innovations such as ATMs, POS terminals, and international cards (VISA, MasterCard, Amex, and UnionPay) on the financial performance of commercial banks operating in Ethiopia.

1.1 Statement of the problem

Financial innovation is a broad term used to describe the generation of new and creative approaches to different circumstances. Schumpeter [45] defines innovation as a change

in the shape of the production function. He categorizes innovations as being either “process” that permits an existing product or service to be provided more cheaply, or “product or service” that is new to the market. Financial innovation is the unanticipated improvement in the array of financial products and instruments that are stimulated by unexpected change in customer needs and preferences, tax policy, technology, and regulatory impulses [10].

The role of innovations in economic development is indisputable. The general definitions of innovations explain that they appear when new ideas, solutions, and instruments are implemented in order to change the conditions of the business entity and to improve its situation. The application of innovations increases the competitiveness of a business entity and creates value for its owners [12] p. 196; [22] p.116. They are crucial in the economic development process. They can reduce the intermediaries' and the clients' transaction costs, and as a result brings about widening, deepening, and integration of financial markets. This process thereby accelerates economic growth by stimulating savings, investment, and production.

Financial innovations are used by banks as formidable strategic variables to outstrip the competition. They have become an essential means for the bank to improve its performance and to maintain its effectiveness on the market [9]. A successful innovation thus generates a proprietary competitive position that bestows on the firm a competitive advantage and superior performance [31].

The most familiar financial innovations adopted in African countries are ATMs and Point of Sale (POS). They are categorized as the essential elements for financial service delivery. These services ensure efficient payment and settlement systems are in place. In some African countries, [15] stated that the number of ATMs and POS remains limited. For example, in 2010, Botswana counted 21 ATMs and 288 POS terminals per 100,000 people, while in South Africa, the number of ATMs and POS stood at 52 and 700, respectively.

However, with the high reduction in hardware and other supporting infrastructures, the new trend shows that the number of ATMs and POS has been growing at a fast pace in Sub-Saharan Africa. It accounts for the second-highest figure in the world after South Asia. The advent of internet banking has also improved the level of financial services in Africa. It has empowered different organizations with new business models and new ways to offer 24-hour accessibility to their customers [16].

The outcomes of the previous studies on the effect of financial innovation on the financial performance have been empirically inconclusive [11]. Previous studies have produced mixed results regarding the effect of financial innovations on banks financial performance. [41]; [18], in their studies concluded that financial innovations had the least impact on financial performance, while others [9], [36] concluded that financial innovation had a significant contribution to financial performance. [29] puts forward that innovations are not just critical for firms in the financial services industry, but also affect other companies; for instance, enabling them to raise capital in larger amounts and at a lower cost than they could otherwise and that innovation is an important phenomenon in any sector of a modern economy. It is at the center of such mixed conclusions that created and necessitated the need to carry out this study. This gap in the literature also motivated this study as the study sought to answer the research question, what is the effect of financial innovations on the financial performance of commercial banks in Ethiopia?

According to the researcher's empirical review, studies have been done on the effect of financial innovations on the financial performance of commercial banks in different countries. The studies were not performed by using the most recent data. Innovation generally seems to have a positive effect in raising financial performance of the innovators. Since innovations take place now and then, it is also interesting to comprehend its effect on the financial performance of banks at the present time. To this end, the researcher incorporated three financial innovation-related independent variables and identified their effects on the financial performance of banks.

1.2 Objectives of the study

The objective of the study was to examine the effect of financial innovations on financial performance of commercial banks focusing on their effects on net interest margin (NIM).

In line with the above general objective, the specific objectives of the study are:

1. To examine the effect of ATMs on financial performance of commercial banks.
2. To investigate the effect of POS on the financial performance of commercial banks.
3. To analyze the effect of international cards (VISA, MasterCard, Amex, and UnionPay) on the financial performance of commercial banks.

1.3 Research Hypothesis

The study was done based on the following research hypotheses that were derived from empirical evidence and tested throughout the analysis of the study:-

Hypothesis 1: ATM has a positive and significant effect on the profitability of commercial banks.

Hypothesis 2: POS has a positive and significant effect on the profitability of commercial banks.

Hypothesis 8: International Cards (VISA, MasterCard, Amex, and UnionPay) have positive and significant effects on the profitability of commercial banks.

1.4 Scope of the study

The study covers all branches, areas, and districts of commercial banks operating in Ethiopia. The annual reports of those banks were used for analysis, and financial innovations were employed. The financial innovations that have been considered in the study are automated teller machines (ATM), point of sale terminals (POS), and international cards (VISA, MasterCard, Amex, and UnionPay). The researcher made use of published financial statements that are audited and published from 2016 up to 2020 on the banks' official websites. On the other hand, the financial performance of commercial banks was measured with net interest margin (NIM).

1.5 Significance of the study

This study adds more knowledge on the concept of financial innovation and gives more empirical findings on the relationship between financial innovations and performance. This will provide more literal materials that will be of value to scholars, students, and researchers. This study can also be used as a basis for further researches and also in academics in the area of financial innovation. This study will provide an insight into the effect of financial innovation on financial performance. This will provide management of banks in different countries in financial services with more insight on the importance of financial innovations.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Theoretical literature

2.1.1 Financial Innovation

Financial innovation can be defined as the act of creating and then popularizing new financial instruments as well as new financial technologies, institutions, and markets. Innovations are new ideas that consist of: new products and services, new use for existing products, new markets for existing products or new marketing methods [47]. [23] defines financial innovation as a «process of change, a change in the type and variety of available financial products to be sure, but also a change in financial intermediaries and markets themselves. In

the financial services industry, innovation is viewed as the act of creating and popularizing new financial instruments, technologies, institutions, and markets, which facilitate access to information, trading and means of payment and to the emergence of new financial instruments and services, new forms of organization, and more developed and complete financial markets [48].

[2] defined financial innovations relatively narrow as any change in the operations of a financial intermediary. They argue that an innovation may be either cost decreasing or cost increasing for the intermediary and/or for the society. [17] define financial innovation as "...something new that reduces costs, reduces risks or provides an improved product/service/instrument that better satisfies participants' demands..." within a financial system.

[44] take a much broader position, namely that innovations in the sense of technical progress comprise the development of new products (services) or changes in processes, institutions, and market systems that raise efficiency. It should be pointed out that the decreasing cost effect of an innovative financial service, in practice, might be difficult to assess, particularly if the costs are shifted from the financial institution to the client. Thus, what may appear as a cost reduction for the lending institution may in fact be a shift of costs to another level.

2.1.2 Product Innovations

Financial product innovations refer to the introduction of new, or modified financial services, such as new credit, savings, insurance, leasing, hire purchase or other financial products [25]. Product innovations may be introduced to better reflect the demands of the target clientele, to improve efficiency or to expand the institution's market and outreach. They can be vital in securing the institutional viability of the financial intermediary [44].

▪ Automated Teller Machine (ATM)

Automated Teller Machine (ATM) is the first well-known machine to provide electronic access to customers. With the advent of ATMs, banks can serve customers outside the banking hall. ATM is designed to perform the most important function of banks, such as withdrawal of cash, deposits, the printing of mini statements settlements of bills. It does all through access to personal identification number (PIN) and a plastic that contains a magnetic chip which the customers identified through [38].

At first, a bank ATM could only be used by customers who had accounts in that bank. Still in the early 1980s, with the improvement in telecommunications, banks took advantage and started what is called shared ATMs networks where customers of other banks could access their money through other bank's ATMs. Banks paid other ATM owners "interchange" fees to cover the marginal cost of the "of us" transactions. The ATMs were operated using an ATM card which was a magnetic card [26].

▪ Debit Cards

A debit card (also known as a bank card, plastic card, or check card) is a plastic payment card that can be used instead of cash when making purchases. Unlike a credit card, the money comes directly from the user's bank account when performing a transaction. Functionally, it can be called an electronic cheque, as the funds are withdrawn directly from either the bank account or from the remaining balance on the card. In some cases, the cards are designed exclusively for use on the internet, so there is no physical card [33].

▪ Credit Cards

A credit card is a payment card issued to users (cardholders) to enable the cardholder to pay a merchant for goods and services based on the cardholder's promise to the card issuer to pay them for the amounts so paid plus the other agreed charges [46].

▪ **Point of sale terminal (POS)**

According to [14], POS covers a variety of services rendered through machines located at retail establishments. POS terminals are generally clerk-generated devices located at the checkout, or convenience counter or retail establishment. Electronic cash register versions of these terminals have been in operation for several years, maintaining store records on sales, inventories, accounts receivable, and the like. Now, POS devices have been linked to financial institution computers, allowing retail customers to receive approval for check cashing and electronically initiate transfers from their accounts to the retailers. In some installations, customers can make deposits to their accounts. POS devices accept either a plastic credit card or a plastic debit card, depending on whether the customer wants to delay the payment by charging the purchase deducted directly from the customer's account. As electronic POS systems increase, their use will probably replace many of the paper transactions accomplished through cash payments and check and credit transactions.

2.1.3 Financial Performance

External parties normally evaluate a firm's ability based on its performance (Bonn, 2000). This implies why performance is like a mirror to a firm. The level of goal accomplishment generally defines a firm's performance [1]. Firm performance is the outcomes achieved in meeting internal and external goals of a firm [30]. As a multidimensional construct, performance has several names, including growth, survival, success, and competitiveness. The concept of firm growth was introduced in the early 1930s, known as the Law of Proportionate Effect (sometimes called Gibrat's rule of proportionate growth). The Law of Proportionate Effect is frequently used as a benchmark for many studies to determine business growth. [20] explains a firm's growth rate does not depend on the firm size.

Firm performance is a multidimensional construct that consists of four elements [4]. Customer-focused performance, including customer satisfaction and product or service performance; financial and market performance, including revenue, profits, market position, cash-to-cash cycle time, and earnings per share; human resource performance, including employee satisfaction; and organizational effectiveness, including time to market, level of innovation, and production and supply chain flexibility.

Using organizational goals as a basis, different methods are adopted by different firms to measure their performance. This performance indicator can be measured in financial and non-financial terms [7]; [8]. Most firms, however, prefer to adopt financial indicators to measure their performance [21].

There are many different ways to measure financial performance, but all measures should be taken in aggregation. Return on assets (ROA), average annual occupancy rate, net profit after tax, and return on investment (ROI) are the commonly used financial or accounting indicators by firms [49]. Other common measures are profitability, productivity, growth, stakeholder satisfaction, market share, and competitive position [7].

Generally, Performance measures can play a key role in initiating or implementing technological innovations and organizational change through incentives for improving performance and measurements to evaluate progress toward this goal. However, financial elements are not the only indicator for measuring firm performance. It needs to combine with non-financial measurement to adapt to the changes of internal and external environments [28].

2.1.4 Indicators of Financial Performance of Banks

Profit is the ultimate goal of commercial banks. All the strategies designed and activities performed thereof are meant to realize this grand objective. However, this does not mean that commercial banks have no other goals. Commercial banks could also have additional social and economic goals. However, the intention of this study is related to the effect of financial innovations on financial performance (profitability). To measure the

profitability of commercial banks concerning financial innovations, there are a variety of ratios used of which Return on Asset, Return on Equity, and Net Interest Margin is the major ones ([35]; [5]).

➤ **Net Interest Margin (NIM)**

NIM measures the difference between the interest income generated by banks and the amount of interest paid out to their lenders (for example, deposits) relative to the amount of their (interest-earning) assets. It is usually expressed as a percentage of what the financial institution earns on loans in a specific period and other assets minus the interest paid on borrowed funds divided by the average amount of the assets on which it earned income in that period (the average earning assets). The NIM variable is defined as the net interest income divided by total earnings assets [24].

Net interest margin measures the gap between the interest income the bank receives on loans and securities and the interest cost of its borrowed funds. It reflects the cost of bank intermediation services and the efficiency of the bank. The higher the net interest margin, the higher the bank's profit and the more stable the bank is. Thus, it is one of the key measures of bank profitability. However, a higher net interest margin could reflect riskier lending practices with substantial loan loss provisions [27].

2.2 Empirical Review

[3] in his study on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Banking operations in Nigeria using the nature and degree of adoption of innovative technologies; degree of utilization of the identified technologies; and the impact of the adoption of ICT devices on banks, found out that technology was the main driving force of competition in the banking industry. During his study, he witnessed an increase in the adoption of ATMs, EFT, smart cards, electronic home, and office banking, and telephone banking. He indicates that ICT adoption improves the banks' image, and leads to a wider, faster and more efficient market. He asserts that it is imperative for bank management to intensify investment in ICT products to facilitate speed, convenience, and accurate services, or otherwise lose out to their competitors.

[32] researched the effects of financial innovation on the financial performance of commercial banks in South Sudan. The casual research methodology was used to study 16 commercial Banks registered with the central bank of South Sudan for 2009- 2013. Return on Equity (ROE) was used to measure financial performance, and the number of Transactions done using ATM per day (Withdrawals, deposits), the number of transactions done using a phone per day (paying bills, accessing the account (update, checking the balance), borrowing and depositing and The Amount of Money borrowed using internet transactions. The finding shows a positive and moderate linear relationship between the number of daily transactions using ATMs and the financial performance of commercial banks in South Sudan. The number of daily transactions using phones showed a positive but a weak relationship with the financial performance of the commercial banks. Money borrowed showed weak but negative relationship with the financial performance of commercial banks. The study concluded that financial innovation is significant and has a positive impact on the financial performance of the commercial banks in South Sudan.

[51] carried out a study on the effect of financial innovation on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. The population of the study consisted of all 43 commercial banks in Kenya. The primary data for the study was collected in a questionnaire, and secondary data was collected using publication, annual financial statement reports of commercial banks on the website, and the bank supervision annual report from 2006- 2012 which was organized by the Central Bank of Kenya. The actual effect of financial innovation on financial performance was measured by regressing ROA and ROE against 12 financial innovations. The main findings of the study were financial innovations such as number of ATM cards, number of credit cards issued to customers, Number of debit cards issued to customers, number of minor/children account, number of special deposit account, number youth-oriented account, and number of

customers registered for e-banking and number customers registered for mobile banking and number of agency banking had imposed ROA of the bank studied. It concluded that financial innovation shows a significant positive effect on the performance of banks in Kenya.

[39] conducted a study to assess the impact of financial innovations on the profitability of banks in Ghana. It was a case study carried out on Fidelity Bank Ghana Limited. Data for the research was gathered from the Income Statements of the bank within the period of five years 2009-2013 and analyzed by the measure of profitability. Return on Equity (ROE) was used to measure profitability and financial innovation was also assessed using the bank's branches and number of automated teller machines (ATMs) over the period. Variables such as inflation and exchange rate of the domestic currency against the US Dollar over the period were used as control variables for the study. The findings show that both the number of branches and the number of ATMs have a positive relationship with the bank's ROE and concluded that an increase in the level of financial innovations ultimately leads to an increase in the profitability of a bank in Ghana.

[43] conducted a study to examine the impact of Information and Communication Technology and Bank Performance in Nigeria. Secondary data from the bank's annual financial reports and various issues of Factbooks from the Nigerian Stock Exchange in the form of the panels covering the period 2001 – 2011 have been used. Net profits and Return on Equity (ROE) were used as a dependent variable, and explanatory variables were a number of ATM devices and the volume of a transaction on e-banking services of the selected commercial banks. The study concludes that cautious application of ICT apparatus will continue to enhance commercial banks' performance in the country unless otherwise disrupted by externalities.

In 2016, Tilahun was conducted a study to examine the effect of E-banking on the financial performance of commercial banks in Ethiopia [50]. In this study, which covers the period from 2013 to 2015, the research takes three variables Number of ATM, Number of POS and Number of debit cardholders as an independent variable to represent e- banking while profit before tax is used as a dependent variable to measure profitability. Finally, the researcher had concluded that electronic banking had a statistically significant impact on the return on assets and profitability of commercial banks of Ethiopia.

2.3 Conceptual Framework of the study

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework of the study

Source: Researcher's construct (2021)

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The primary aim of this study is to examine the effect of financial innovations on the financial performance of commercial banks in Ethiopia. To achieve this objective, explanatory research design with a quantitative approach was used. Explanatory research design enables the researcher to examine the effect of financial innovation on financial performance.

3.2 Target Population

The target population is the population to which a researcher wants to generalize the study results [34]. The target population of this study includes all Ethiopian commercial banks. The banks financial innovation service reports from annual reports of 2015-2020 were considered.

3.3 Source and Type of data

The study took a quantitative research approach by using secondary data gathered from the banks published annual reports of their official websites. This study was used panel data covering a period of 5 years (2016 to 2020). The Panel data involves the pooling of observations on a cross-section of units over several periods and provides results that are simply not detectable in pure cross-sections or pure time-series studies [11].

[11], states that panel data set has two major advantages; first, it can address a broader range of the issues and tackle the more complex problems than pure time series or pure cross-sectional data alone, and by structuring the model in the appropriate way, the researcher can remove the impact of certain forms of omitted variable bias in the regression result. Second, it is often examined how the relationships between variables change. Hence, by combining cross-sectional data and time-series data, the researcher can increase the degree of freedom, and thus the power of a test, by employing information on the dynamic behavior of a large number of entities at the same time.

3.4 Data Analysis

In this study, quantitative data was gathered from commercial banks annual reports. After that, data was rearranged, edited, and calculated to become complete data needed for this study. Next, the collected panel data was analyzed by using descriptive statistics and linear regression analysis. Descriptive statistics (mean, maximum and minimum values, and standard deviations) were used to analyze the general trends of the data from 2016 to 2020. A linear regression model was used to determine the relative significance of each independent variable in explaining the variation financial performance of commercial banks. The model was conducted by the ordinary listing square (OLS) method using SPSS Version 21 software package.

According to [11], ordinary least square (OLS) or linear least square is a method to estimate the slope and intercept in a linear regression model. This study will use an ordinary least square (OLS) regression to estimate the linear equation. The rationale for choosing OLS is that if the Classical Linear Regression Model (CLRM) assumptions hold, then the estimators determined by OLS will have several desirable properties and are known as Best Linear Unbiased Estimators [11]. In addition, as noted in [40], OLS outperforms the other estimation methods when the following holds; the cross-section is small, and the time dimension is short. Therefore, as far as the above facts hold in this study, it is rational to use OLS.

3.5 Model specification

The model specification refers to determining which independent variables should be included in or excluded from a regression equation. In general, the specification of a regression model should be based primarily on theoretical considerations rather than empirical or methodological ones. A multiple regression model is, in fact, a theoretical statement about the causal relationship between one or more independent variables and a dependent variable [6].

Model specification is the first and most critical stage of regression analysis, followed by estimation of parameters and interpretation of those parameters. The estimates of parameters of a model and the interpretation of them depend on the correct specification of the model [6]. Regression analysis is also valuable for quantifying the impact of various simultaneous influences upon a single dependent variable. Further, because of omitted variables bias with simple regression, multiple regressions are often essential even when the researcher is only interested in the effects of one of the independent variables.

According to [11], the general multivariate regression model with K independent variables can be written as follows:-

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \dots + \beta_k X_{ki} + \epsilon_i \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$$

Where Y_i is the i^{th} observation of the dependent variable, $X_{1i} \dots X_{ki}$ are the i^{th} observation of the independent variables, β_0, \dots, β_k are the regression coefficients, ϵ_i is the i^{th} observation of the stochastic error term, and n is the number of observations. Hence, the effect of financial innovations on the financial performance of commercial banks can be modeled as follow:-

$$NIM = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ATM_t + \beta_2 POS_t + \beta_3 IC_t + \epsilon$$

Where:-

- NIM - Net Interest Margin
- ATM - Number of ATM machines
- POS - Number of POS terminals
- IC – Number of International Card Holders
- B_0 = Constant term
- $\beta_1, 2, 3$ are parameters to be estimated;
- ϵ = is the error component for the bank at time t assumed to have mean zero $E[\epsilon_{it}] = 0$
- t = the index of time period, and = 1 – 5; the year from 2016 up to 2020.

3.6 Operationalization of study variables

Table 3.1: Definition, notation, and expected sign of explanatory variables

	Variables	Notation	Measure	Expected sign
Dependent Variable	Net Interest Margin	NIM	$\frac{\text{Interest Revenue} - \text{Interest Expenses}}{\text{Average Earning Assets}}$	
Independent Variables	Number of International Card Holders	IC	Natural logarithm of number of international cardholders	+
	Number of ATM machines	ATM	Natural logarithm of number of ATM machines	+
	Number of POS terminal	POS	Natural logarithm of number of POS terminals	+

Source: Researcher’s construct (2021)

4. Results and discussions

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 4.1 summarizes descriptive statistics of the dependent and independent variables for commercial banks from the years 2016 to 2020. The table shows the mean, minimum, maximum, standard deviation, and number of observations for the dependent variable Net Interest Margin (NIM) and independent variables number of ATMs, number of POS terminals (POS), and the number of international cardholders (IC).

Table 4.1 Descriptive statistics

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Net Interest Margin	.027320	.049290	.03956020	.007935424
Number of ATM Machines	220	7389	814.80	163.837
Number of POS Terminals	827	20397	10500.80	768.976
Number of International Card Holders	43300000	109400000	7334000.00	260336.897

Source: Linear regression model output, 2021

Table 4.1 displays the average indicators of variables computed from the financial statements and the standard deviation that shows how much dispersion exists from the average value. According to [11], a low standard deviation indicates that the data point tends to be very close to the mean. In contrast, high standard deviation indicates that the data point is spread out over a large range of values. It shows the summary data for the variables used in the analysis. The data are average values across years and reported showing the trend of the key variables over 2016 to 2020. The data shows that from 2016 to 2020, the average profit level, NIM of commercial banks was 3.956 percent. And also, the standard deviation is 0.007935 as, indicated in table 4.1. This implies that the volatility of the NIM ratio varies from the mean by 0.7935%.

4.2 Linear regression model result

Econometric analysis was undertaken to examine the effects of financial innovations on financial performance of commercial banks in Ethiopia. As previously explained, a linear regression model was employed to estimate the effects of hypothesized explanatory variables on the financial performance. The model was used to fulfill the specific objectives of the study, i.e. to examine the number of ATM Machines, number of POS Terminals, and number of international cardholders that affect the financial performance of the study area.

Table 4.2 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.708 ^a	.641	.596	.000331334

a. Predictors: (Constant), Number of International Card Holders, Number of POS Terminals, Number of ATM Machines

Source: Linear regression model output, 2021

Table 4.2 provides the R and R^2 values. The R -value represents the simple correlation and is 0.708 (the "R" Column), which indicates a high degree of correlation between the number of international cardholders, number of POS terminals and number of ATMs on the one hand and financial performance of the bank on the other hand. The R^2 value (the "R Square" column) indicates how much of the total variation in the dependent variable, financial performance is explained by the independent variables (number of international cardholders, number of POS terminals, and number of ATMs).

The next table is the ANOVA table, which reports how well the regression equation fits the data (i.e., predicts the dependent variable) and is shown below:

Table 4.3 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.000	3	.000	764.465	.027 ^b
	Residual	.000	80	.000		
	Total	.000	84			

a. Dependent Variable: Net Interest Margin

b. Predictors: (Constant), Number of International Card Holders, Number of POS Terminals, Number of ATM Machines

Source: Linear regression model output, 2021

Table 4.3 indicates that the regression model predicts the dependent variable significantly well. Looking at the "Regression" row and go to the "Sig." column, the study indicates the statistical significance of the regression model that was run. Here, Sig. or p-value of 0.027, which is less than 0.05, and shows that, overall, the regression model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable (it is a good fit for the data).

The Coefficients table provides the necessary information to predict financial performance from the number of ATMs, number of POS terminals, and number of international cardholders. Likewise, it shows figures used to determine whether the independent variables of the study contribute statistically significantly to the model (by looking at the "Sig." column). Furthermore, the values in the "B" column under the "Unstandardized Coefficients" column are used as shown below:

Table 4.4 Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.004	.001		3.410	.182
1 Number of ATM Machines	.000	.000	1.035*	16.355	.039
Number of POS Terminals	1.055E-005	.000	.358**	8.848	.072
Number of International Card Holders	7.683E-009	.000	.252	3.533	.176

a. Dependent Variable: Net Interest Margin

* and ** indicate that the coefficients are statistically significant at 5% and 10% level respectively

Source: Linear regression model output, 2021

$$NIM = 0.004 + 0.000ATM + 1.055POS + 7.683IC + \epsilon$$

The coefficient for a number of ATMs (.000) is statistically significantly different from 0 using an alpha of 0.05 because its p-value is 0.039, which is smaller than 0.05. Likewise, the coefficient for the number of POS terminals (1.055) is statistically significant at the 0.1 level since the p-value or sig. (0.072) is less than .01. However, the coefficient for the number of international cardholders (7.683) is statistically significant because its p-value or sig. of 0.176 is greater than .05 and 0.1.

Sig.: It determines whether the association between the independent variable and dependent variable is statistically significant by comparing the p-value (sometimes called the prob-value) of the independent variable with the chosen significance level. The association is statistically significant, and the null hypothesis is rejected when the p-value (value listed in the column called "Sig.") is smaller than or equals to the specified significant level like .05 or .01 or 0.1. Whereas, when p-value listed in the sig. column is greater than the specified significance level, the association between the independent variable and dependent variable is statistically insignificant.

4.3 Elaboration on Significant Explanatory Variables

Table 4.5 Hypotheses and results of significant independent variables

Independent Variables	Notation	Expected Sign/Hypothesis	Result from linear regression model
The number of ATMs	ATM	+ (High number of ATMs, high financial performance)	β of 1.035; number of ATMs has a Positive & significant effect on the financial performance of banks
The number of POS terminal	POS	+ (High number of POS terminals, high financial performance)	β of 0.358; positive association between number of POS terminals and financial performance of banks

Source: Researcher's construct (2021)

- 1) **The number of ATMs:** It was hypothesized that ATMs has a positive and significant effect on the profitability of commercial banks. The result from the linear regression model in above table 4.4 and table 4.5 indicates a positive sign for the number of ATMs variable (β of 1.035), which implies a positive association between the number of ATMs and the financial performance of banks. This shows that holding other explanatory variables remains constant; as the number of ATMs increases, ATM cardholders can enhance their access to banking service (cash withdrawal), which results in the improvement of banks income in particular and financial performance in general. Since the Sig. statistic or p-value in some other statistical application (0.039) is smaller than the chosen significance level (0.05 or 5 percent), the positive association between the number of ATMs and Financial Performance is statistically significant, i.e. the level of ATMs contributes to the enhancement of banks' profitability. The finding of this study agrees with the study findings on the effects of ATMs on the profitability of banking in different countries. For instance, the study result by [3] performed in Nigeria showed that the increase in the adoption of ATMs had a positive impact on a bank's image and its profitability.
- 2) **Number of POS terminals (POS):** It was hypothesized that POS has a positive and significant effect on the profitability of commercial banks. The result from the linear regression model in the above table 4.4 and table 4.5 shows a positive sign for the number of POS terminals variable (β of 0.358), which implies that holding other explanatory variables remains constant, there is a positive relationship between the number of POS terminals and the financial performance of banks. Since the Sig. statistic or p-value (0.072) is smaller than the chosen significance level (0.1 or 10 percent)), the positive association between the number of POS terminals and the financial performance is statistically significant. The positive association between the number of POS machines and financial performance of commercial banks could be attributed to the fact that POS terminals have provided an opportunity for the banks to establish agent banking in non-traditional bank locations. It also supports the bank to improve its profitability through income generated in the form of charge fees and by reduction of the bank's operational costs. And also, it can increase customer satisfaction because it allows customers to purchase, pay bills and access statements without going to the bank. The finding of this study agrees with the study finding of [14].

5. Conclusions

According to the outputs of a linear regression model performed by the SPSS version 21 [see table 4.4 and table 4.5], the number of ATMs and the number of POS terminals are positively related to the financial performance of banks. This study similarly evidenced that another variable, which is the number of international cardholders (VISA, MasterCard, Amex, and UnionPay), does not have a significant effect on the financial performance of banks. This may be because the number of transactions conduct by subscribers of the international cards was small, and not enough for the bank to generate a large amount of service charge or income. Hence, except for research hypothesis 3, all research hypotheses are accepted.

6. Scope for Further Research

This study encourages further, and comprehensive research into the interconnection between process innovations (Real Time Gross Settlement, Automated Clearing House, Electronic Funds Transfer, SWIFT, and others), institutional innovations (Agency banking, Internet banking and Mobile banking) and other financial innovations, on the one hand, and financial performance of banks (commonly measured in terms of ROA and ROE) on the other hand. As well, the researcher suggests the potential researchers broaden the scope of the study to the commercial banks operating in Africa to confirm the findings of this study.

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